

**Enhanced Photocatalysis by Defect-engineered CeO₂ with Sulfite Activation
under Visible Light Irradiation**

Yaning Han^{a,b}, Xiaowei Chen^{b,c,}, Miguel Tinoco^b, Susana Fernández-García^b, Ana B.*

Hungria^{b,c}, Youxun Li^d, Jiyuan Nai^a, Ren'an Wu^e, José J. Calvino^{b,c}, Lei Jiang^{a,}*

^a Center for Bioengineering and Biotechnology, College of Chemical Engineering, China University of Petroleum (East China), Qingdao 266580, China;

^b Departamento de Ciencia de los Materiales, Ingeniería Metalúrgica y Química Inorgánica, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Cádiz, Campus Río San Pedro, Puerto Real, Cádiz E-11510, Spain

^c Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Microscopía Electrónica y Materiales (IMEYMAT), Universidad de Cádiz, Campus Río San Pedro, Puerto Real, Cádiz E-11510, Spain

^d Marine Science Research Institute of Shandong Province, Qingdao 266104, China

^e CAS Key Laboratory of Separation Sciences for Analytical Chemistry, Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Dalian 116023, China

*** Corresponding Authors:** Lei Jiang (leijiang@upc.edu.cn) and Xiaowei Chen (xiaowei.chen@uca.es)

Abstract

Sulfite-based advanced oxidation processes (s-AOP) have recently garnered significant attention due to their ability to generate highly oxidative sulfate radicals and eliminate contaminants from water, utilizing the conventional pollutant SO_2 . A state-of-the-art platform has been developed through the synergistic combination of s-AOP and photocatalysis under weak visible light. This platform achieved the enhanced oxidation efficiency for defect-engineered nanofacets of Pr-doped CeO_2 nanocubes. The reaction pathways, intermediates, ion leaching and the possible influence of aqueous conditions during the methyl orange degradation have been investigated. The $\text{CeO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3/\text{vis}$ -light platform exhibits promising prospect as a system to enhance conventional s-AOP in wastewater treatment or disinfection. It demonstrates good performance in terms of pH sensitivity, anion influence, and resistance to leaching. This highlights its significant potential for practical applications and future process scale-ups.

Key words: sulfite, photocatalysis, Pr-doped CeO_2 , defect, degradation

1. Introduction

While chemical production plays a crucial role in the global economy, its significance comes with a sobering downside, posing a substantial threat to our environment through pollution. The advanced oxidation process (AOP), such as Fenton reaction, is one of the most effective wastewater treatment technologies. It employs HO^\bullet radicals ($E^0 = +2.7 \text{ eV}$) to effectively break chemical bonds in organic compounds, thereby degrading these pollutants into smaller molecules. Recently, sulfite-based advanced oxidation processes (s-AOP) have attracted much attention for their dual capability, i.e. generating highly oxidative $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ radicals ($E^0 = +3.1 \text{ eV}$) and employing sulfite ions as key agents sourced from conventional SO_2 , an air pollutant [1]. Furthermore, s-AOP also can be conducted under UV-visible irradiation to facilitate the process, where sulfite serves as a hole scavenger. This prevents the recombination of electrons with holes, thus enhancing the activity of the photocatalyst [2]. Classical photocatalysts, such as TiO_2 and ZnO , have been utilized in photocatalytic s-AOP. However, these catalysts still exhibit low catalytic efficiencies [3].

To the best of our knowledge, the catalysts commonly employed for sulfite activation consist primarily of both homogeneous and heterogeneous transition metals, along with their corresponding oxides or sulfides [4]. However, catalysts based on rare earth oxides have yet to be explored as potential alternatives, aiming for a greener and more efficient $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ precursor. As one of the most well-known and extensively studied rare earth oxides, CeO_2 exhibits excellent catalytic activities for many kinds of reactions. This is attributed to the exchange of Ce^{3+} and Ce^{4+} redox couples, as well as the presence of numerous oxygen vacancies ($\text{VO}^{\bullet\bullet}$). Meanwhile, it was reported that photocatalytic effects, together with a high degree of defect tunability, make it a promising candidate for enhancing visible photocatalytic performance through the introduction of defects. Zhang et al. introduced Cu_2O doping into CeO_2 to create a p-n heterojunction structure, aiming to effectively segregate photogenerated holes from electrons and enhance visible light absorption [5]. Cai et al. reported that Fe^{3+} doping led to an increase in Ce^{3+} concentration, which subsequently improved the catalytic activity of CeO_2 [6]. Similar results were observed by Channei et al. [7] who prepared Fe-doped CeO_2 using a combination of homogeneous precipitation and impregnation methods, and synthesized photocatalytic thin films.

Compared to common Fe^{3+} and Cu^{2+} dopants, Pr has an atomic number much closer to Ce and their ionic radii are similar. Therefore, Pr can replace Ce in the lattice of CeO_2 without altering its original crystal structure [8, 9]. It has been demonstrated that Pr doping increases the $\text{VO}^{\bullet\bullet}$ concentration, which can enhance the adsorption of reactant molecules [10, 11]. Moreover, being a rare earth oxide, Pr possesses a unique 4f orbital that can create an intermediate energy level for CeO_2 . This leads to a reduced bandgap of CeO_2 and an improvement in its photocatalytic performance. It has been shown that the introduction of defects such as tensile strain, point defect, and lattice strain seems to be an effective approach to improve the photocatalytic activity of CeO_2 [12, 13]. In many cases, these defects themselves serve as active or co-catalytic sites [14]. The introduction of defects can affect the geometry and electronic structure of the original

active center, usually leading to a higher number of unsaturated sites, which have an open structure and easily trap reactants ^[15].

In this study, we constructed a photocatalytic sulfite-based advanced oxidation process (s-AOP) system for degradation of methyl orange (MO) using CeO₂ with different morphologies. Our investigation was extended to understand the influence of defects, including Pr doping and nanofacets, on the activity of photocatalytic activation of sulfite under visible irradiation, along with the synergistic effects of photo-sulfite interactions. A proposed reaction mechanism has been outlined, and we systematically investigated the influence of aqueous conditions, such as sulfite concentration, initial pH values, and ions, aiming to elucidate a broader application potential of the synergistic CeO₂/Na₂SO₃/vis-light system.

2. Experimental

CeO₂ nanocubes (CeO₂ NC) and Pr-doped CeO₂ nanocubes with varying Pr concentrations (5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%), denoted as 5%Pr-CeO₂ NC, 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC, 15%Pr-CeO₂ NC, and 20%Pr-CeO₂ NC+NR, as well as ceria nanocubes with reconstructed nanofacets (CeO₂ NC O600, 5%Pr-CeO₂ NC O600, 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC O600, and 15%Pr-CeO₂ NC O600), were synthesized following previously described methods ^[8]. The sample labeled as 20%Pr-CeO₂ NP was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (US). All the samples were characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) on an instrument D8 ADVANCE (Bruker), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) on an Axis Ultra DLD apparatus (Kratos), and inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES) using an Iris Intrepid equipment (Thermo Elemental). Additionally, high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) images were acquired in a JEOL 2010-F microscope, while scanning transmission electron microscopy-high angle annular dark field (STEM-HAADF) images and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) compositional maps were obtained using an aberration-corrected FEI Titan3 Themis 60-300 microscope ^[8].

Raman spectra of the ceria samples were measured using a confocal dispersive Raman spectrometer (LabRAM HR Evolution, HORIBA, Japan) in backscattering configuration. UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectra (UV-Vis DRS) were examined using a UV-2600 spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan), and radicals were quantified through electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy using DMPO as the spin trap with an EMX Plus instrument from Bruker (Germany). Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) specific surface areas were measured by nitrogen adsorption at -196 °C on ASAP 2020 and TriStar II 3020 (Micromeritics), X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) analysis was conducted using the AXIOS-Petro instrument from PANalytical B.V. to obtain an average value of the chemical composition from several random spots on the compressed samples ^[16].

Photocatalytic sulfite-activated oxidation was performed under visible light (30 mW/cm²) emitted from a Xenon lamp (CEL-HXUV300, Beijing Zhongjiao Jinyuan Technology, China) with a 420 nm filter. Ceria catalysts were added to 40 mg/L MO solution and allowed to adsorb MO in the dark for 30 min before the addition of Na₂SO₃

and the commencement of visible light irradiation. The degradation of MO was monitored using an UV-vis spectrometer (UV8000, Shanghai Metash Instruments, China). The identification and analysis of degraded intermediates or products were carried out using a Solarix Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (FT-ICRMS) equipped with a 15 T superconducting magnet (Bruker Daltonics GmbH, Bremen, Germany). The obtained mass spectroscopy data were processed by Data Analysis 4.2 software from Bruker. The leaching of Ce after 2 h of oxidation reactions was measured by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (ICP-OES, Agilent7800, US).

Various radical inhibitors, such as methanol and ethanol (Xilong Chemical, China) to scavenge hydroxyl radicals ($\text{HO}\cdot$) and sulfate radicals ($\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$)^[17, 18], tetramethylpiperidine (Sigma-Aldrich) for superoxide radicals ($\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$)^[19] and sodium oxalate (Alfa Aesar) for holes (h^+)^[20], were introduced to the reaction mixture. This addition aimed to identify potential radicals involved in the sulfite-based degradation process. Fluorescent probes, including coumarin^[21] and 1,3-diphenylisobenzofuran (DPBF)^[22], were utilized to investigate hydroxyl radicals at 322 nm excitation and superoxide radicals at 420 nm excitation, respectively, by fluorescence spectrometer (FluoroMax-4, Horiba Jobin Yvon, France). All other chemicals were procured from Sigma-Aldrich (US).

3. Result and discussion

3.1 Characterization of pure and Pr-doped CeO_2 samples

CeO_2 samples with different morphologies and Pr-doping concentrations were synthesized using a hydrothermal method previously described^[8]. As shown in Fig. 1a - 1d, a well-defined nanocube (NC) shape is maintained up to 15 mol.% Pr. However, 20% Pr doping led to a mixture of NC and nanorod (NR) morphologies (Fig. 1e). Therefore, the highest Pr doping concentration in ceria explored in this study is 20 mol.%. Meanwhile, a commercially available sample consisting of ill-defined Pr-doped CeO_2 nanoparticles, denoted as 20% Pr-doped CeO_2 NP, was included for comparison (Fig. 1f). The Pr doping concentration in this commercial sample was determined to be approximately 20%, as measured by XRF analysis, while its particle size ranges from 30 to 100 nm. EDX element maps of all samples demonstrate the uniform distribution of Pr and Ce both in the bulk and on the surface of doped samples (Fig. S1).

Figure 1. STEM-HAADF images of (a) CeO₂ NC, (b) 5%Pr-CeO₂ NC, (c) 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC, (d) 15%Pr-CeO₂ NC and TEM images of (e) 20%Pr-CeO₂ NC+NR and (f) 20%Pr-CeO₂ NP.

Given previous reports indicating that an oxidation pretreatment induces the formation of the zig-zag (111) type nanofacets on the (110) surfaces of both pure^[23] and Pr-doped ceria nanocubes^[8], ceria samples were oxidized at 600 °C under a 5% O₂/He flow. As depicted in Fig. 2, TEM results confirm the formation of sawtooth-like nanofacets on CeO₂ nanocubes with various Pr-doping concentrations up to 15 mol.%. These sawtooth-like nanofacets primarily represent^[24] surfaces, which could potentially enhance the adsorption of reactants and consequently boost the catalytic activity of the ceria samples^[13].

Comentado [AH1]: I don't want to change anything in the references, but reference 23 should be ACS Catal. 2015, 5, 3504–3513

Comentado [AH2]: I don't understand what you want to express with this sentence, more active surfaces?

Figure 2. HRTEM image of (a) CeO₂ NC O600 and STEM-HAADF images of (b) 5%Pr-CeO₂ NC O600, (c) 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC O600, and (d) 15%Pr-CeO₂ NC O600.

XRD patterns for all the nanoceria synthesized above reveal a fluorite-like phase, representing a face-centered cubic lattice of CeO₂ (Fig. S2). No significant angular shift

was observed in the XRD patterns of Pr-doped CeO₂ samples with varying Pr concentrations, owing to the similar cationic radii of Pr³⁺ (96 pm) and Ce⁴⁺ (97 pm) [9]. UV-vis diffuse absorption spectra (Fig. 3a) indicate that all samples showed strong absorbance in the UV region (<350 nm), attributed to electron transfer from O 2p to Ce 4f [25]. A broad absorption in 400 – 600 nm region was observed after Pr-doping, suggesting the interfacial polaron effect emerging from electron–phonon interaction and increased oxygen vacancies when some Ce⁴⁺ ions in the lattice are replaced by Pr³⁺ ions [8].

Figure 3. (a) UV-vis diffuse reflectance spectra and (b) Raman spectra of 15% Pr-CeO₂ O600 and 20%Pr-CeO₂ NP in comparison with CeO₂ NC, CeO₂ NC O600, 10% Pr-CeO₂ NC and 10% Pr-CeO₂ NC O600 from our previous reports [8, 9].

The indirect and direct band gap energies (E_g) were subsequently calculated from the UV-vis diffuse reflectance spectra results using the Kubelka-Munk function [26] and are summarized in Table 1. Pr-doping does not alter the direct band gap energies, which remain around 3.5 eV, consistent with the typical band gap range (3.2 ~3.6 eV) of CeO₂ materials [27]. The indirect band gap energy of pure CeO₂ NC is ~0.3 eV lower than the direct band gap energy. By comparing the indirect band gap energy of CeO₂ NC O600, Pr-doped ceria oxidized at 600 °C, and 20%Pr-CeO₂ NP, it is evident that the indirect band gap energy decreases with increasing Pr doping. This phenomenon is likely attributed to the truncated crystal structure and atomic structure distortion on the surface of nanoparticles [8]. A smaller indirect band gap effectively promotes the jump of electrons from the valence band (VB) to the conduction band (CB). Therefore, the reduction in indirect band gap energy observed with both Pr doping and 600 °C treatment suggests the existence of an easier electron pathway for these defected samples.

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of CeO₂ with different ratios of Pr doping

Sample	BET surface area (m ² /g)	ICP (mol.%)		XPS (mol.%)		Indirect E_g (eV)	Direct E_g (eV)
		Ce	Pr	Ce	Pr		
CeO ₂ NC	38	--	--	--	--	3.17	3.50

Comentado [SF3]: On the table you really notice a lot of unfilled gaps. I assume that this is due to a lack of results. However, most of the absence of these results is noticeable in the nanofaceted samples. I suggest that this table be placed in Supporting Information indicating the variables where there are more results but only with the nanofaceted samples, and in this table 1 that the non-oxidised samples be reflected. Maybe this way it will not impact so many blank spaces.

CeO ₂ NC O600	18	--	--	--	3.19	3.49
5%Pr-CeO ₂ NC ^a	26	95.6	4.4	88.1	11.9	
5%Pr-CeO ₂ NC O600	21					
10%Pr-CeO ₂ NC ^a	25	90.3	9.7	90.6	9.4	2.95
10%Pr-CeO ₂ NC O600 ^a	20			89.2	10.8	2.86
15%Pr-CeO ₂ NC ^a	23	85.6	14.4	74.9	25.1	
15%Pr-CeO ₂ NC O600 ^a	--					2.91
20%Pr-CeO ₂ NC+NR ^a	25	80.8	19.2	64.2	35.8	
20%Pr-CeO ₂ NP	35	79.7	20.3	58.7	41.3	3.51

^a: XPS and Eg results were reported in our previous work [8, 9].

Ceria materials exhibit an excellent oxygen storage capacity due to the facile exchange of the Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ redox couple, resulting in a common type of point defect - oxygen vacancy. This formation introduces a new defective energy level that facilitates electron transitions between the conduction band (CB) and valence band (VB) [28]. Oxygen vacancies (VO^{••}) in ceria samples were characterized using Raman spectroscopy in this study. Fig. 3b shows a characteristic Raman band at around 466 cm⁻¹ [29] in the ceria-containing samples, corresponding to the F_{2g} symmetric stretching vibration in the symmetric breathing mode of the Ce-O₈ vibrational unit [30]. This band shifts toward lower wavenumber 451 cm⁻¹ with more Pr-doping for two possible reasons. One is that the substitution of one Ce⁴⁺ ion with two Pr³⁺ ions may lead to an increase in the concentration of VO^{••} defects in the lattice [31]. The other is that Pr-doping can slightly alter the bond lengths and atomic geometrical configurations of Ce-O and Pr-O, and thus affect the vibrational properties of the lattice. Furthermore, the introduction of Pr results in a significant D-band at 572 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 3b) and its intensity ratio to the F_{2g} band (I_D/I_{F_{2g}}) can indicate the amount of VO^{••} in a semi-quantitative way [32].

It is worth noting that Raman spectrum may vary depending on the ability of the samples to absorb the excitation wavelength [33]. For instance, the Raman spectra of CeO₂ NC and CeO₂ NC O600 primarily represent the signals from their bulks since these catalysts exhibit no absorbance at 532 nm (Fig. 3a), which is the excitation wavelength used for Raman measurement. In contrast, the samples with Pr doping exhibit a strong absorbance at 532 nm, indicating that the resonance Raman signals mainly originate from the surface of the samples. Therefore, the increase in the I_D/I_{F_{2g}} ratio can be also an indicator of an increase in catalyst surface defects. Table 1 shows that I_D/I_{F_{2g}} for 15% Pr-CeO₂ NC O600 (1.08) is much higher than 10% Pr-CeO₂ NC O600 (0.38), followed by 10% Pr-CeO₂ NC (0.25), suggesting that VO^{••} increase in the nanocubes can be achieved by both Pr doping and ceria NC surface reconstruction at high temperature. The I_D/I_{F_{2g}} ratio for the commercial 20%Pr-CeO₂ NP sample is 0.74.

Comentado [SF4]: Would it be a problem to put the results back in this table, even if they were previously published? If there would be no problem, it would be advisable to place them, in order to clearly see the comparison.

Comentado [SF5]: When you say "all" it seems to say all the synthesized samples. Figure 3b doesn't show all the synthesized samples.

Comentado [SF6]: I don't know, but this is correct, isn't it?

Comentado [SF7]: I don't find this data in Table 1, but within Figure 3b.

The BET specific surface areas of almost all samples were also listed in Table 1. After the 600 °C treatment, the BET specific surface area of CeO₂ NCs slightly decreased. For example, the surface area decreased from 25 m²/g to 20 m²/g for the 10% Pr-CeO₂ NC sample. Despite the high-temperature process generating more nanofacets on the surface, some of the ceria nanoparticles aggregated. This aggregation might be the reason for the observed decrease in surface areas. Meanwhile, ICP measurements were employed to quantify the amounts of Ce and Pr in the samples (Table 1). These results align well with the expected Pr concentrations in the samples. However, the Pr concentrations on the surface of Pr-doped ceria samples, except for 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC, are higher than those in the bulk, as indicated XPS results. Further Pr 3d XPS analysis (Fig. S3) shows that the surface of commercial 20% Pr-CeO₂ NP sample was dominated by Pr³⁺ with negligible Pr⁴⁺, in agreement with previous studies on 10% Pr-CeO₂ NC and 10% Pr-CeO₂ NC O600 samples [8].

3.2 Sulfite-activated oxidation for degradation of MO under visible light

The catalytic activity of CeO₂ in activating sulfite for the degradation of methyl orange (MO), monitored through its UV-vis absorbance at 464 nm, was evaluated. The ceria nanoparticles were incubated in the MO solution for 30 minutes before the addition of sulfite, allowing for the physisorption of MO (approximately 7%, as shown in Fig. 4). A substantial removal of MO (> 95%) occurred only when Na₂SO₃, 20%Pr-CeO₂ NP, and visible light were present simultaneously at room temperature (25 °C). In the absence of the visible light or Na₂SO₃, the removal of MO was no more than 17%, probably due to the highly oxidizing ability of Pr-doped ceria [8, 9] to cause the oxidative degradation of MO. In order to exclude the potential influence from the increased temperature (up to 6 °C after 2 h irradiation), a similar experiment was conducted at 35 °C. Fig. 4 shows that the higher temperature resulted in an increase of the total removal rate of no more than 20% (from < 17 % to 37%). This observation suggests that most of the degradation of MO in the mixture was induced by the photocatalysis under visible light.

Figure 4. The degradation of 40 mg/L MO with time and varying conditions including 1mg/mL 20%Pr-CeO₂ NP, 40 mM Na₂SO₃, and/or visible light (30 mW/cm²).

Furthermore, several CeO₂ samples with well-defined morphologies and zigzag nanofacets (Table 1) were tested to investigate the synergy between sulfite activation and photocatalysis (Fig. 5a). The first-order reaction rate constant K can be obtained by fitting $-\ln(C/C_0)$ vs time from Fig. 5a to demonstrate the kinetics of catalytic degradation. It was found that all the tested samples with defects, such as Pr-doping and 600 °C treatment, demonstrated an increase in the reaction rate (Fig. 5b). Among all the nanocubes, 15% Pr-CeO₂ NC O600 exhibited the best performance, with a K value three times higher than 15% Pr-CeO₂ NC. Herein, two additional types of nanoceria were introduced and compared with ceria nanocubes. One is the synthesized 20% Pr-CeO₂ NC+NR and the other is the commercial 20% Pr-CeO₂ NP. Both samples demonstrated relatively high degradation efficiency compared with other ceria nanocube catalysts, partly because nanorods and nanoparticles (Fig. 1) possess much more defects than nanocubes.

Considering the effect of the specific surface area on the activity of nanocatalysts, the maximum absorbance change of MO was normalized by the BET surface area of each CeO₂, *i.e.* $\Delta A/\text{BET area}$, to compare catalytic activity per unit area on the surface of nanoceria (Fig. 5c). The activity increases with the rising doping rate, this superiority may be attributed to two reasons related to surface defects. The first reason is the increased oxygen vacancies when more Pr³⁺ cations replace Ce⁴⁺ cations, as confirmed by Raman spectroscopy (Fig. 3b) [31]. The second reason is the presence of generated sawtooth (111) nanofacets with more edges and defects after high-temperature treatment.

Comentado [SF8]: Formato: Sugiero colocar la leyenda fuera de la gráfica, y que la escala "time" indicarla hasta 130 minutos.

Comentado [SF9]: ??

Figure 5. (a) The degradation of 40 mg/L MO under different conditions including 0.5 mg/mL CeO₂, 40 mM Na₂SO₃ and visible light (30 mW/cm²). (b) The corresponding first-order reaction rate K . (c) ΔA_{\max} at 464 nm normalized with the BET specific surface area of different CeO₂ catalysts.

3.3 Semi-quantitative analysis on the synergy

As illustrated schematically in Fig. 6a, the synergy between s-AOP and photocatalysis is based on a three-element photo-sulfite system, i.e., CeO₂ catalyst, Na₂SO₃, and visible light. Herein K_{AOP} is defined as the primary reaction rate constant of s-AOP (with only CeO₂ and Na₂SO₃) and K_{vis} is for photocatalytic system (with only CeO₂ and vis-light). The hypothesis is that, if s-AOP is independent of photocatalysis, or there is no synergy, the overall reaction rate K would be equal to the sum of K_{AOP} and K_{vis} . However, if s-AOP inhibits photocatalysis, or the opposite, K should be smaller than ($K_{AOP} + K_{vis}$). Alternatively, if there is synergy between s-AOP and photocatalysis, K should be higher than the sum of ($K_{AOP} + K_{vis}$).

A comprehensive comparison of K , K_{AOP} , and K_{vis} from different CeO₂ samples is then shown in Fig. 6b with full details in Fig. S4. The overall reaction rates K are significantly higher than those of K_{AOP} and K_{vis} , separately or combined, suggesting a strong synergy between CeO₂-induced photocatalysis and s-AOP. A synergy factor (SF) is calculated to represent the difference between K and ($K_{AOP} + K_{vis}$) as in Eq. 1, together

with the corresponding percentage of synergy (SF%) as in Eq. 2. Using these two semi-quantitative parameters, Figs. 6b and 6d show the dominating role of synergy in the photo-sulfite system, with SF% at 78 – 88% for all samples.

$$SF = K - (K_{AOP} + K_{vis}) \quad (1)$$

$$SF\% = \frac{SF}{K} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Figure 6. (a) Schematic demonstration of the photo-sulfite oxidation system composed of catalyst, sulfite and visible light with the corresponding reaction rates and possible synergistic reaction pathways. (b) First-order reaction rate of MO degradation in presence of different CeO₂ catalysts. (c) Contribution percentages of synergistic effect. [CeO₂] = 0.5 mg/mL, [Na₂SO₃] = 40 mM, visible light = 30 mW/cm².

3.4 Mechanism and reaction pathways for photocatalytic sulfite-activated oxidation of MO degradation

In order to identify possible active species or intermediates in the photo-sulfite-reactions mentioned above, several radical scavengers were added to the reaction mixture respectively, including ethanol and methanol for HO[•] and SO₄^{•-}, sodium oxalate for h⁺, and tetramethylpiperidine for O₂^{•-}. Figs. 7a and 7b illustrate that all the studied scavengers can significantly inhibit the reaction, suggesting the involvement of all these species in the reactions. Based on the previously reported sulfite-activated oxidation by other redox metal oxides [34], a possible CeO₂ mediated pathway for sulfite activation is listed in Eq. 3-10 as well as in Fig. 6a and 7b.

The exposure of CeO₂ to visible light is expected to separate highly oxidative h⁺ and reductive electrons at the same time, both of which participate in the generation of more active species, as shown in Eq. 11-13. Additionally, the presence of oxygen vacancies VO^{••} may also contribute to generate sulfite radicals (SO₃^{•-}) and O₂^{•-} (Eq. 14, 15) [35], leading to the formation of peroxomonosulfate radicals (SO₅^{•-}) and sulfate radicals (SO₄^{•-}) depicted in Eq. 5-8.

Fluorescent probes for HO[•] and O₂^{•-} can be employed to quantify the amounts of generated radicals from different CeO₂ samples. Coumarin serves as a fluorescent probe for HO[•] with a characteristic emission at 436 nm for the formed 7-hydroxycoumarin [21, 36, 37]. Fig. 7c reveals that CeO₂ catalysts can cause an increase in fluorescent intensity. The higher Pr doping, the greater fluorescent intensity, which is in line with the observation in Figs. 5a and 5b. Similar results were obtained for O₂^{•-} with the DPBF probe at 420 nm (Fig. 7d) [22, 38]. CeO₂ NC with 10-20% Pr doping quenches almost all fluorescence, suggesting a high O₂^{•-} level. Furthermore, EPR spectroscopy results in Fig. 7e shows a clear signal for DMPO-SO₃^{•-} adduct (α_N=14.7 G, α_H= 16.0 G) after the addition of Na₂SO₃ to the mixture of CeO₂ and MO under visible light [39], confirming the generation of sulfite radicals. No signal for DMPO-SO₄^{•-} was observed in the EPR spectra, probably because of the excess DMPO trapping SO₃^{•-}, which prevents the subsequent production of SO₄^{•-} through a chain radical reaction (Eq. 3-15).

Figure 7. (a) Effects of radical scavengers (20 mM) on the MO degradation by 0.5 mg/mL 20% Pr- CeO_2 NP and 40 mM Na_2SO_3 under 30 mW/cm^2 visible light. (b) The comparison of first-order reaction rate K after different scavenger additions. The inset shows the possible radical chain reactions. (c) Fluorescent spectra of 0.15 mg/mL coumarin in a mixture of 40 mM Na_2SO_3 , and 0.5 mg/mL ceria catalyst under 30 mW/cm^2 visible light. (d) Fluorescent spectra of 0.01 mg/mL DPBF in similar conditions as in (c). (e) EPR spectra during the MO degradation in presence of 0.5 mg/mL 20%Pr- CeO_2 NP and 40 mM Na_2SO_3 under 30 mW/cm^2 visible light.

The synergistic effect between s-AOP and photocatalysis for the degradation of MO may be related to the capability of Na_2SO_3 to scavenge h^+ , subsequently mitigating the recombination of electron-hole pairs, and thus improving the photocatalytic activity of the pure and Pr-doped ceria catalysts. A detailed demonstration of the MO degradation is shown in the energy level diagrams in Fig. 8 with all the highly oxidizing species highlighted in red. As shown in previous work [8], the direct band gap energy of CeO_2 NC is 3.50 eV, with E_{CB} at -0.69 eV and E_{VB} at 2.81 eV (Fig. 8). In general, the relative energy levels of E_{VB} , E_{CB} and E_0 can determine the feasibility of electron transfer between CeO_2 and the adsorbed organic compounds [40]. Pr doping in CeO_2

introduced an additional 4f energy level and $\text{VO}^{\bullet\bullet}$ located between the band gaps of Ce 4f and O 2p [25], both leading to the decrease of band gap, making it easier to absorb photons of visible light (1.62 – 3.11 eV). The photogenerated electrons help to convert the adsorbed oxygen molecules on the surface of the catalyst into active species, such as $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$. Meanwhile, the photogenerated hole⁺ in the valence band may react with SO_3^{2-} , initiating radical chain reactions that ultimately result in the formation of $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$.

Figure 8. Mechanism of Pr-CeO₂/Na₂SO₃ photocatalytic oxidation reaction with the energy level diagrams

During the catalytic degradation of MO, it is suggested that the highlighted red oxidizing radicals in Fig. 8 may oxidize MO [41] (Eq. 16), leading to the formation of intermediates. These intermediates then undergo either self-degradation or further degradation into the final products (Eq. 17).

Mass spectrometry was employed to identify possible degraded intermediates or products at different irradiation intervals (Fig. S5). MO is a large organic big molecule and its primary peak was observed at m/z of 304 [42], accompanied by some additional peaks at $m/z = 331, 261, 290, 293, 189, 152, 201$ etc. All the m/z values less than the mother peaks correspond to segments of the MO molecules detected by mass spectroscopy. At reaction time of 60 min, the intensity of the $m/z = 304$ peak dramatically decreased, suggesting the degradation of MO. Meanwhile, the intensities of m/z peaks at 261, 293 and 276 increased. Several new peaks ($m/z = 94, 136, 177, 283, 255, 214, \text{ and } 239$), corresponding to intermediates and products of degradation, became apparent. The m/z peak of 304 vanished entirely at the photocatalytic reaction time of 120 min. The primary degradation products were 261 and 293, followed by 283, 190, 255, 277, 239, and 214. The intensities of 94, 136, and 177 remained unchanged from 60 to 120 min, indicating their minor presence in the products.

Two possible degradation pathways are proposed in Fig. 9 by combining our

results with previous reports [41, 43, 44]. One involves the cleavage of the N-C bond of dimethylamino groups to eliminate one or two methyl groups ($m/z = 290$ or 276), followed by the deamination to form new intermediate and product ($m/z = 261$). This pathway stands out as the primary degradation route of MO under the studied conditions in this work, evident from the predominant m/z peak at 261 in the products after 2 hours of reaction. The intensities of the $m/z = 283$, 189, and 255 peaks are notably smaller than those of 261 and 290. The origin of the m/z peak at 283 is unclear, and no corresponding reports have been found in the literature. It is postulated that it might originate from the first degradation product at $m/z = 290$, where seven hydrogen atoms were removed. The cleavage of the azo bond ($-N=N-$) leads to the formation of smaller molecules, such as $m/z = 94$ [43]. For the other pathway, SO_2 was removed with the incorporation of an oxygen atom in the benzene ring ($m/z = 255$) [45, 46], or the azo bond was cleaved symmetrically to generate 4-amino sulfonic acid ($m/z = 177$) [47] and N,N-dimethyl p-phenylenediamine ($m/z = 136$) [48]. The extremely weak intensities of these two peaks suggest that only a small fraction of MO undergoes degradation through this pathway. Eventually, all the small molecules or short-chain carboxylic acids can be oxidized to open rings and degraded to inorganic ions, CO_2 and H_2O (Fig. 9) [49].

Figure 9. Two possible degradation pathways of MO, highlighted in blue and red arrows.

3.5 Applications

The effects of CeO_2 catalyst amount, Na_2SO_3 concentration, initial solution pH, salt presence, and light intensity were further studied in the applications of $\text{CeO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3/\text{vis}$ -light system (Fig. 10). The reaction rate increased with the amount of CeO_2 catalyst (Fig. 10a) and Na_2SO_3 concentration (Fig. 10b) until reaching a plateau at approximately 23.9 min^{-1} . Excessive CeO_2 may aggregate, while an excess of Na_2SO_3 could potentially react with radicals, inhibiting or impeding degradation reactions. Although the literature reports pH-dependence in sulfite-activated oxidation by transition metals or metal oxides [50, 51], our study reveals that the initial pH value of the aqueous solution has minimal impact on the CeO_2 -mediated photo-sulfite oxidation process (Fig. 10c). Herein, sulfuric acid and sodium hydroxide were used to adjust the pH values instead of buffers to avoid possible influence from other anions. The

negligible effect of pH was probably due to the complex chain network (Fig. 7) involved in generation of the oxidative radicals, which encompasses both H^+ and OH^- (Eq. 1-13). The active radicals react with MO through various pathways, with a high system complexity leading to more stable oxidation products. As a result, the dominant presence of either H^+ or OH^- ions in the solution are preferentially consumed during the reaction, ultimately resulting in the neutralization of the solution with the final pH value between 7 and 8 (Fig. 10d).

Figure 10. Effect of (a) CeO₂ catalyst amount and (b) Na₂SO₃ concentrations, as well as (c) initial pH values on the degradation rate of 40 mg/L MO under 30 mW/cm² visible light; (d) Change of pH values of solution before and after the reaction; (e) Influence of co-existing anions including 6 mM HCO₃⁻, 3.5 mM HPO₄²⁻ or 8.6 mM Cl⁻ on the degradation of 40 mg/L MO in the mixture of 0.5 mg/mL 20%Pr-CeO₂ NP, 40 mM Na₂SO₃ and 30 mW/cm² visible light; (f) Effect of light intensity.

Knowing the possible impacts of the anions (HCO₃⁻, Cl⁻, etc.^[34, 52]) in reacting with SO₄^{•-} to generate radicals like CO₃^{•-}^[34], Cl[•], Cl₂^{•-}^[52], several salts (NaHCO₃, Na₂HPO₄, and NaCl) were added separately to the photo-sulfite oxidation system. Fig.10e shows that none of the co-existing anions has notable inhibitory or quenching effect, probably due to the stability of complex network for radical generation, as discussed above. As expected, higher light intensity leads to an increase of the catalytic activity (Fig. 10f). It is worth noting that the power intensity of visible light in this study

(30 mW/cm²) is almost comparable to the ambient indoor daylight (approximately 27 mW/cm² as measured in Qingdao, China, at 11 a.m. in May). This intensity is much lower than the levels often employed in previous studies, which have reached up to 100 mW/cm² cm² [53-58], indicating its substantial potential for practical applications. Moreover, ICP analysis was employed to investigate the possible leaching of Ce in the photo-sulfite reactions. Results show that the leaching ratio of Ce after 6.9 mg/mL CeO₂ NC reaction with SO₃²⁻ was 0.0012%, which may be considered as negligible or environmentally friendly reactions [59].

4 Conclusion

Defect-engineered CeO₂ nanomaterials are utilized to establish a photo-sulfite oxidation platform, integrating a sulfite-based oxidation process with photocatalysis under weak visible light. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that the rare earth oxide CeO₂ is reported to participate in the sulfite-based reactions in synergy with photocatalysis. The oxidation pathway and the mechanism on the MO degradation were investigated and the effects of defects such as Pr-doping, nanofacets and oxygen vacancies were studied together with the identification of active radicals and intermediates. Our results show the dominant roles of photo-sulfite synergy and the highly oxidative radicals such as SO₄^{•-} in the effective degradation under visible sunlight as weak as ambient indoor daylight. The reaction rates of CeO₂-mediated photo-sulfite reactions were systematically compared under various aqueous conditions. The CeO₂/Na₂SO₃/vis-light system emerged as a promising platform, showcasing enhanced performance in conventional s-AOP for wastewater treatment or disinfection. Its notable attributes include pH sensitivity, resistance to anion influence, and a low leaching ratio, suggesting significant potential for practical applications and scalability in various processes.

Acknowledgement

This work received financial support from the Natural Science Foundation of Shandong Province (No. ZR2017LB028), the Key R&D Program of Shandong Province (Nos. 2018GSF118032 and 2022CXGC020415). Projects with reference numbers PID2020-113809RB-C33 and PID2022-142312NB-I00 from the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities of Spain are also acknowledged. Yaning Han would like to express gratitude to the University of Cadiz in Spain for the predoctoral FPI-UCA grant (UCA/REC67VPCT/2021).

Reference

- [1] G. Crini, E. Lichtfouse, Advantages and disadvantages of techniques used for wastewater

- treatment, *Environmental Chemistry Letters*. 17 (1) (2018) 145-155. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10311-018-0785-9>.
- [2] G.T. Güyer, K. Nadeem, N. Dizge, Recycling of pad-batch washing textile wastewater through advanced oxidation processes and its reusability assessment for turkish textile industry, *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 139 (2016) 488-494. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.08.009>.
- [3] A. Fujishima, X. Zhang, D. Tryk, TiO_2 photocatalysis and related surface phenomena, *Surface Science Reports*. 63 (12) (2008) 515-582. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.surfrep.2008.10.001>.
- [4] S. Wu, L. Shen, Y. Lin, K. Yin, C. Yang, Sulfite-based advanced oxidation and reduction processes for water treatment, *Chemical Engineering Journal*. 414 (2021). <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ccej.2021.128872>.
- [5] S. Hu, F. Zhou, L. Wang, J. Zhang, Preparation of $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{CeO}_2$ heterojunction photocatalyst for the degradation of acid orange 7 under visible light irradiation, *Catalysis Communications*. 12 (9) (2011) 794-797. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.catcom.2011.01.027>.
- [6] W. Cai, F. Chen, X. Shen, L. Chen, J. Zhang, Enhanced catalytic degradation of AO7 in the $\text{CeO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2$ system with Fe^{3+} doping, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*. 101 (1-2) (2010) 160-168. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2010.09.031>.
- [7] D. Channei, B. Inceesungvorn, N. Wetchakun, S. Ukritnukun, A. Nattestad, J. Chen, S. Phanichphant, Photocatalytic degradation of methyl orange by CeO_2 and Fe-doped CeO_2 films under visible light irradiation, *Sci Rep*. 4 (2014) 5757. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/srep05757>.
- [8] L. Jiang, M. Tinoco, S. Fernandez-Garcia, Y. Sun, M. Traviankina, P. Nan, Q. Xue, H. Pan, A. Aguinaco, J.M. Gonzalez-Leal, G. Blanco, E. Blanco, A.B. Hungria, J.J. Calvino, X. Chen, Enhanced artificial enzyme activities on the reconstructed sawtoothlike nanofacets of pure and pr-doped ceria nanocubes, *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*. 13 (32) (2021) 38061-38073. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acsami.1c09992>.
- [9] L. Jiang, S. Fernandez-Garcia, M. Tinoco, Z. Yan, Q. Xue, G. Blanco, J.J. Calvino, A.B. Hungria, X. Chen, Improved oxidase mimetic activity by praseodymium incorporation into ceria nanocubes, *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*. 9 (22) (2017) 18595-18608. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acsami.7b05036>.
- [10] Z. Bian, J. Zhu, S. Wang, Y. Cao, X. Qian, H. Li, Self-assembly of active $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ visible photocatalyst with ordered mesoporous structure and highly crystallized anatase, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. 112 (16) (2008) 6258-6262. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp800324t>.
- [11] S. Hao, J. Hou, P. Aprea, F. Pepe, Mesoporous Ce-Pr-O solid solution with efficient photocatalytic activity under weak daylight irradiation, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*. 160-161 (2014) 566-573. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2014.06.013>.
- [12] C. Yang, Y. Lu, L. Zhang, Z. Kong, T. Yang, L. Tao, Y. Zou, S. Wang, Defect engineering on CeO_2 -based catalysts for heterogeneous catalytic applications, *Small Structures*. 2 (12) (2021). <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/sstr.202100058>.
- [13] Y. Wu, W. Xu, L. Jiao, Y. Tang, Y. Chen, W. Gu, C. Zhu, Defect engineering in nanozymes, *Materials Today*. 52 (2022) 327-347. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.mattod.2021.10.032>.
- [14] Y. Wu, J. Wen, W. Xu, J. Huang, L. Jiao, Y. Tang, Y. Chen, H. Yan, S. Cao, L. Zheng, W. Gu, L. Hu, L. Zhang, C. Zhu, Defect-engineered nanozyme-linked receptors, *Small*. 17 (33) (2021) e2101907. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/sml.202101907>.
- [15] F. Bai, L. Xu, X. Zhai, X. Chen, W. Yang, Vacancy in ultrathin 2d nanomaterials toward sustainable energy application, *Advanced Energy Materials*. 10 (11) (2019).

- <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201902107>.
- [16] J. Hampel, P. Wallace, N. Tripcevich, T. Teague, Preparation of pressed powder samples for xrf trace element analysis., UC Berkeley: Archaeological Research Facility. (1991).
- [17] G. Li, Y. Guo, Y. Jin, W. Tan, F. Liu, H. Yin, Intrinsic mechanisms of calcium sulfite activation by siderite for atrazine degradation, *Chemical Engineering Journal*. 426 (2021). <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.131917>.
- [18] X. Duan, C. Su, J. Miao, Y. Zhong, Z. Shao, S. Wang, H. Sun, Insights into perovskite-catalyzed peroxymonosulfate activation: Maneuverable cobalt sites for promoted evolution of sulfate radicals, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*. 220 (2018) 626-634. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2017.08.088>.
- [19] X. Ma, H. Hao, W. Sheng, F. Huang, X. Lang, Bridging green light photocatalysis over hierarchical nb2o5 for the selective aerobic oxidation of sulfides, *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*. 9 (2021) 2214-2222. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1039/d0ta10757c>.
- [20] N.A. Lima, G.C. Mendonça, G.T.S.T. da Silva, B.S. de Lima, E.C. Paris, M.I.B. Bernardi, Influence of the synthesis method on cuwo4 nanoparticles for photocatalytic application, *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*. 32 (2021) 1139-1149. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10854-020-04887-2>.
- [21] K. Hirano, T. Kobayashi, Coumarin fluorometry to quantitatively detectable oh radicals in ultrasound aqueous medium, *Ultrason Sonochem*. 30 (2016) 18-27. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ultsonch.2015.11.020>.
- [22] T. Ohyashiki, M. Nunomura, T. Katoh, Detection of superoxide anion radical in phospholipid liposomal membrane by fluorescence quenching method using 1,3-diphenylisobenzofuran, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Biomembranes*. 1421 (1) (1999) 131-139. [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0005-2736\(99\)00119-4](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0005-2736(99)00119-4).
- [23] M. Tinoco, S. Fernandez-Garcia, A. Villa, J.M. Gonzalez, G. Blanco, A.B. Hungria, L. Jiang, L. Prati, J.J. Calvino, X. Chen, Selective oxidation of glycerol on morphology controlled ceria nanomaterials, *Catalysis Science & Technology*. 9 (9) (2019) 2328-2334. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1039/c9cy00273a>.
- [24] P. Burroughs, A. Hamnett, A.F. Orchard, G. Thornton, Satellite structure in the x-ray photoelectron spectra of some binary and mixed oxides of lanthanum and cerium, *Journal of the Chemical Society, Dalton Transactions*. (17) (1976). <https://dx.doi.org/10.1039/dt9760001686>.
- [25] B. Choudhury, P. Chetri, A. Choudhury, Oxygen defects and formation of ce3+ affecting the photocatalytic performance of ceo2 nanoparticles, *RSC Adv*. 4 (9) (2014) 4663-4671. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1039/c3ra44603d>.
- [26] V. Pandey, N. Singh, F.Z. Haque, Enhancement in structural and optical properties of boron doped zno nanostructures synthesized by simple aqueous solution growth technique, *Journal of Advanced Physics*. 6 (3) (2017) 358-366. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1166/jap.2017.1333>.
- [27] Z. Wang, Z. Quan, J. Lin, Remarkable changes in the optical properties of ceo(2) nanocrystals induced by lanthanide ions doping, *Inorg Chem*. 46 (13) (2007) 5237-42. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ic0701256>.
- [28] S. Chen, H. Wang, Z. Kang, S. Jin, X. Zhang, X. Zheng, Z. Qi, J. Zhu, B. Pan, Y. Xie, Oxygen vacancy associated single-electron transfer for photofixation of co2 to long-chain chemicals, *Nat Commun*. 10 (1) (2019) 788. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-08697-x>.

- [29] I.d.C. Silva, F.A. Sigoli, I.O. Mazali, Reversible oxygen vacancy generation on pure ceo₂ nanorods evaluated by in situ raman spectroscopy, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. 121 (23) (2017) 12928-12935. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.7b03155>.
- [30] R.N. Bharathi, S. Sankar, Structural, optical and magnetic properties of pr doped ceo₂ nanoparticles synthesized by citrate–nitrate auto combustion method, *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*. 29 (8) (2018) 6679-6691. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10854-018-8654-7>.
- [31] J.R. McBride, K.C. Hass, B.D. Poindexter, W.H. Weber, Raman and x-ray studies of ce_{1-x}re_xo_{2-y}, where re=la, pr, nd, eu, gd, and tb, *Journal of Applied Physics*. 76 (4) (1994) 2435-2441. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.357593>.
- [32] M. Liu, X. Wu, S. Liu, Y. Gao, Z. Chen, Y. Ma, R. Ran, D. Weng, Study of ag/ceo₂ catalysts for naphthalene oxidation: Balancing the oxygen availability and oxygen regeneration capacity, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*. 219 (2017) 231-240. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2017.07.058>.
- [33] Z.-Y. Pu, J.-Q. Lu, M.-F. Luo, Y.-L. Xie, Study of oxygen vacancies in ce_{0.9}pr_{0.1}o_{2-δ} solid solution by in situ x-ray diffraction and in situ raman spectroscopy, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. 111 (50) (2007) 18695-18702. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp0759776>.
- [34] W. Wu, X. Zhao, G. Jing, Z. Zhou, Efficient activation of sulfite autoxidation process with copper oxides for iohexol degradation under mild conditions, *Sci Total Environ*. 695 (2019) 133836. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.133836>.
- [35] S.-R. Zhu, J.-N. Yang, Y. Liu, W. Gao, X. Yi, H. Zhou, M. Wu, Synergetic interaction of lithium cobalt oxide with sulfite to accelerate the degradation of organic aqueous pollutants, *Materials Chemistry and Physics*. 249 (2020). <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2020.123123>.
- [36] K.-i. Ishibashi, A. Fujishima, T. Watanabe, K. Hashimoto, Detection of active oxidative species in tio₂ photocatalysis using the fluorescence technique, *Electrochemistry Communications*. 2 (3) (2000) 207-210. [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1388-2481\(00\)00006-0](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1388-2481(00)00006-0).
- [37] B. Jiang, Y. Liu, J. Zheng, M. Tan, Z. Wang, M. Wu, Synergetic transformations of multiple pollutants driven by cr(vi)-sulfite reactions, *Environ Sci Technol*. 49 (20) (2015) 12363-71. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b03275>.
- [38] Y. Seto, H. Ohtake, M. Kato, S. Onoue, Development of fluorometric reactive oxygen species assay for photosafety evaluation, *Toxicol In Vitro*. 34 (2016) 113-119. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tiv.2016.03.019>.
- [39] X. Zhao, W. Wu, G. Jing, Z. Zhou, Activation of sulfite autoxidation with cu₂e₄ prepared by mof-templated method for abatement of organic contaminants, *Environ Pollut*. 260 (2020) 114038. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.114038>.
- [40] W. He, H. Jia, W.G. Wamer, Z. Zheng, P. Li, J.H. Callahan, J.-J. Yin, Predicting and identifying reactive oxygen species and electrons for photocatalytic metal sulfide micro–nano structures, *Journal of Catalysis*. 320 (2014) 97-105. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jcat.2014.10.004>.
- [41] L.V. Trandafilović, D.J. Jovanović, X. Zhang, S. Ptasińska, M.D. Dramićanin, Enhanced photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue and methyl orange by zno:Eu nanoparticles, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*. 203 (2017) 740-752. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2016.10.063>.
- [42] B. Harikumar, M.K. Okla, I.A. Alaraidh, A. Mohebaldin, W. Soufan, M.A. Abdel-Maksoud, M. Auffy, A.M. Thomas, L.L. Raju, S.S. Khan, Robust visible light active conio(2)-bifeo(3)-nis

- ternary nanocomposite for photo-fenton degradation of rhodamine b and methyl orange: Kinetics, degradation pathway and toxicity assessment, *J Environ Manage.* 317 (2022) 115321. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115321>.
- [43] C.H. Nguyen, C.-C. Fu, R.-S. Juang, Degradation of methylene blue and methyl orange by palladium-doped tio₂ photocatalysis for water reuse: Efficiency and degradation pathways, *Journal of Cleaner Production.* 202 (2018) 413-427. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.08.110>.
- [44] N. Guy, S. Cakar, M. Ozacar, Comparison of palladium/zinc oxide photocatalysts prepared by different palladium doping methods for congo red degradation, *J Colloid Interface Sci.* 466 (2016) 128-37. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2015.12.009>.
- [45] Q.B. Nguyen, D.P. Vu, T.H.C. Nguyen, T.D. Doan, N.C. Pham, T.L. Duong, D.L. Tran, G.L. Bach, H.C. Tran, N.N. Dao, Photocatalytic activity of bitao₄ nanoparticles for the degradation of methyl orange under visible light, *Journal of Electronic Materials.* 48 (5) (2019) 3131-3136. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11664-019-07066-0>.
- [46] X.-f. Lü, H.-r. Ma, Q. Zhang, K. Du, Degradation of methyl orange by uv, o₃ and uv/o₃ systems: Analysis of the degradation effects and mineralization mechanism, *Research on Chemical Intermediates.* 39 (9) (2012) 4189-4203. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11164-012-0935-9>.
- [47] K. Govindan, A.K. Suresh, T. Sakthivel, K. Murugesan, R. Mohan, V. Gunasekaran, A. Jang, Effect of peroxomonosulfate, peroxydisulfate and hydrogen peroxide on graphene oxide photocatalytic performances in methyl orange dye degradation, *Chemosphere.* 237 (2019) 124479. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.124479>.
- [48] G.K. Parshetti, A.A. Telke, D.C. Kalyani, S.P. Govindwar, Decolorization and detoxification of sulfonated azo dye methyl orange by *Kocuria rosea* mtcc 1532, *J Hazard Mater.* 176 (1-3) (2010) 503-9. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2009.11.058>.
- [49] B. Sharma, R. Deswal, Single pot synthesized gold nanoparticles using hippophae rhamnoides leaf and berry extract showed shape-dependent differential nanobiotechnological applications, *Artif Cells Nanomed Biotechnol.* 46 (sup2) (2018) 408-418. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/21691401.2018.1458034>.
- [50] Y. Li, P. Gan, R. Jiang, Z. Zhao, J. Ye, W. Liu, M. Tong, J. Liang, Insight into the synergetic effect of photocatalysis and transition metal on sulfite activation: Different mechanisms for carbamazepine and diclofenac degradation, *Sci Total Environ.* 787 (2021) 147626. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147626>.
- [51] J. Xu, W. Ding, F. Wu, G. Mailhot, D. Zhou, K. Hanna, Rapid catalytic oxidation of arsenite to arsenate in an iron(iii)/sulfite system under visible light, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental.* 186 (2016) 56-61. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2015.12.033>.
- [52] J. Hu, H. Dong, J. Qu, Z. Qiang, Enhanced degradation of iopamidol by peroxydisulfate catalyzed by two pipe corrosion products (cuo and delta-mno₂), *Water Res.* 112 (2017) 1-8. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.01.025>.
- [53] Z. Wang, W. Qiao, M. Yuan, N. Li, J. Chen, Light-intensity-dependent semiconductor-cocatalyst interfacial electron transfer: A dilemma of sunlight-driven photocatalysis, *J Phys Chem Lett.* 11 (6) (2020) 2369-2373. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.0c00315>.
- [54] L. Hu, H. Hu, W. Lu, Y. Lu, S. Wang, Novel composite bifeo₃/zno₂ and its high photocatalytic performance under white led visible-light irradiation, *Materials Research Bulletin.* 120 (2019). <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.materresbull.2019.110605>.

- [55] H. Lee, J.-W. Park, Titanium-doped stainless steel nanotubes for the photocatalytic degradation of an organic compound, *Catalysis Today*. 340 (2020) 268-276. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2018.09.021>.
- [56] G. Atun, S. Ortaboy, E.T. Acar, S.Y. Aydoğan, Photocatalytic efficiency of titania nonylphenol ethoxylate composite thin films under solar irradiation, *Materials Chemistry and Physics*. 275 (2022). <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2021.125210>.
- [57] J. Darabdhara, S. Roy, M. Ahmaruzzaman, Efficient photocatalytic degradation of an organic dye by the fabrication of a novel ternary composite based on zeolitic imidazolate framework via a facile in-situ synthetic approach, *Inorganic Chemistry Communications*. (2023). <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.inoche.2023.110694>.
- [58] P.J. Mafa, B. Ntsendwana, B.B. Mamba, A.T. Kuvarega, Visible light driven znmo₄/bifewo₆/rgo z-scheme photocatalyst for the degradation of anthraquinonic dye, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. 123 (33) (2019) 20605-20616. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.9b05008>.
- [59] H. Su, D. Zhang, P. Antwi, L. Xiao, X. Deng, Z. Liu, B. Long, M. Shi, M.J. Manefield, H.H. Ngo, Exploring potential impact(s) of cerium in mining wastewater on the performance of partial-nitrification process and nitrogen conversion microflora, *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 209 (2021) 111796. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2020.111796>.